

APPENDIX A. QUESTIONNAIRE ITEMS

Note: The ride-hailing platform is referred to as “XYZ” to preserve confidentiality. All questionnaire items refer to the same platform evaluated by the respondents.

Item	Statement
Trust	
T1	I believe that the XYZ application protects my personal data securely.
T2	I believe that XYZ drivers are trustworthy and provide safe services.
T3	I believe that the XYZ application functions reliably without technical disruptions.
Service Quality	
SQ1	The XYZ application provides fast and responsive services.
SQ2	XYZ drivers provide friendly and courteous services.
SQ3	The features of the XYZ application make the booking process easier for me.
Perceived Usefulness	
PU1	Using the XYZ application makes my transportation booking process easier.
PU2	Using the XYZ application improves the efficiency of my daily activities.
PU3	Overall, I find the XYZ application useful.
Perceived Ease of Use	
PEOU1	I find the XYZ application easy to use.
PEOU2	Using the XYZ application enables me to reach my destination easily.
PEOU3	Overall, I find the XYZ application easy to understand.
Attitude Using	Toward
ATU1	I feel that the XYZ application and its features will remain relevant to my needs in the future.
ATU2	I have a positive attitude toward using the XYZ application.
ATU3	I feel motivated to use the XYZ application in the future.
Behavioral Intention	
BI1	I intend to continue using the XYZ application in the future.
BI2	I intend to use the XYZ application in various situations.
BI3	I intend to recommend the XYZ application to others.
Actual System Use	
AU1	I use the XYZ application in accordance with the established procedures.
AU2	I provide accurate information when using the XYZ application.

Item	Statement
AU3	I use the XYZ application according to the appropriate time or duration when needed.
